

TENSILE RESPONSE OF CARBON NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A promising technique to develop polymer matrix nanocomposites from nanophased filaments is described. Linear Low Density Polyethylene (LLDPE) powder and carbon nanoparticles/whiskers are dry mixed and made into continuous filaments by hot extrusion through a small orifice under a high shear force. After extrusion, the filament is partially cooled by chilled air, dried, and continuously wound in a spool. The filaments are then laid in roving, stacked in a unidirectional fashion, and consolidated in a compression molding machine to come up with laminated structures. Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) were performed to compare the thermal stability of as-fabricated nanocomposites with the neat polymer. Tensile coupons were then extracted both in longitudinal $[0^0]$ and transverse directions $[90^0]$ and tested in a Minimat Tester. It was found that with the addition of 2% by weight of nano-whiskers in LLDPE, the tensile strength and modulus of the composite has increased by 21% and 20% respectively. The $[0^0]$ and $[90^0]$ coupons have also demonstrated to have directional effects in tensile response which is believed to have been caused by the alignment of nanowhiskers during the extrusion process. The percentage of crystalline nature and crystal structure of carbon nanoparticles and whisker of as-fabricated composites were identified by the X-ray diffraction pattern. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) studies were also conducted to investigate the morphology of the as-fabricated materials. Details of the fabrication procedures, synthesis of nanocomposites, and mechanical testing are presented in this paper.

KEYWORDS: Carbon nanoparticles, nano-whiskers, Polyethylene, Extrusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

It has been established in recent years that polymer based nanocomposites reinforced with a small percentages of nanoparticles significantly improve the mechanical, thermal and barrier properties of the pure polymer matrix [1–6]. Moreover, these improvements are achieved through conventional processing techniques without any detrimental effects on processability, appearance, density and ageing performance of the matrix. Eventually, these composites are now being considered for a wide range of applications including packaging, coating, electronic, automotive and aerospace industries.

When enhancements in mechanical properties are major concern, it is observed that in case of spherical-shaped particles, improvement in stiffness is easily achievable. However, the improvements in strength are not always achieved. It is believed that the possibility of enhancement in strength is directly related to the load transfer mechanism between the filler particle and the matrix at their interfaces. It can be revealed that as the aligned rod-shaped fillers can introduce higher surface area per particle than the spherical particles, they can contribute

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more in the load transfer mechanism which in turn ensures higher strength of their composites. As result, the scope of research on aligned rod-shaped fillers is increasing day by day. Recently, vapor grown carbon fibers (VGCF) was introduced with much smaller dimensions than traditional fillers [7, 8]. As these types of fibers have attractive aspect ratios, several researchers attempted to develop suitable techniques to align discontinuous fibers along preferred directions within the composite materials [9-11]. Among several fiber aligning techniques, 'Extrusion' has been found as one of the most widely used fiber-aligning methods [12-15]. However, the term 'Extrusion' indicates a kind of process which involves some factors that should be carefully considered in order to establish a successful fiber aligning technique. The starting materials and their chemical compositions, their mixing techniques, type of extruder, material loading process, extrusion temperature, material residence time within the extruder, the die and its orifice shape and size, extrusion rate, extrusion direction, surrounding air temperature and its speed, filaments cooling type and process, filament draw ratio and winding speed, all are significant factors that can dramatically alter the end products and in some cases may result unacceptable products. Considering the properties of vapor grown carbon fibers it seems that they can be used for fiber alignment using extrusion. However, the major problem associated with VGCF is that they become highly agglomerated, randomly aligned and entangled during production. Therefore, standard composite processing technique may need to be modified to accomplish better results using VGCF. But from commercial point of view, the modifications of composite processing technique may not possible always. In that case, fillers like VGCF with less agglomeration and less entanglement will be highly desirable.

In the present investigation, a new type of carbon fibers called carbon nanowhiskers have been used with the Linear Low Density Polyethylene (LLDPE). These whiskers are developed by an innovative Catalytic Chemical Vapor Deposition (CCVD) process. The end products in this process contain rod-shaped whiskers as a bulk mass. In addition to the bulk material, the product contains significant percentage of nano-sized carbon particles. The characteristic of these types of fibers is that the degree of agglomeration is surprisingly small which enables their easier miscibility with matrix polymers. In our study, 2% by weight of these whiskers were mixed with LLDPE to fabricate aligned polyethylene-whisker composite filaments by conventional extrusion process. The resulting filaments were then stacked in unidirectional manner and consolidated to fabricate nanocomposites panel. In parallel, a control panel was also fabricated from the neat LLDPE to measure any enhancement or degradation of properties. Moreover, to investigate the presence of any positive effect of extrusion process, another panel was fabricated from direct consolidation of dry-mixed whisker and LLDPE powders.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The carbon nanowhiskers were obtained from *Nanotek. Inc.*, which were produced by Catalytic Chemical Vapor Deposition (CCVD) process. In this process dry Nickel (Ni) and Copper (Cu) powder were mixed thoroughly at a ratio of 7:3 and then placed in a reactor as catalysts for the process. The reactor was evacuated and filled with Helium (He) gas to create an inert atmosphere. Ethylene (C₂H₄) and Hydrogen (H₂) gas were introduced into the reactor. The reactor was then heated to 800°C for 30 minutes. Within this period the C₂H₄ and H₂ decomposed and allowed carbon whiskers to grow. The material produced in this method contained rod shaped whiskers of 2-8 μm in diameter and about 100-200 μm in length. It also contained some percentage of 50-200 nm size particles. The whiskers were semi-crystalline in nature and its average density was around 1.8 g/cm³. A commercial grade LLDPE-5202 was procured from *ExxonMobil Chemical*. The LLDPEs were specifically designed to provide good processability and ease of blending. A mechanical crusher was used to produce the micron sized fine powder

which enabled its compatibility to uniform mixing with other particles and also to conventional extrusion process. The density of LLDPE-5202 was 0.926 g/cm³. The melting point is 125°C and decomposition temperature is 489°C. The tensile strength is 8-12 MPa and flexural modulus is 0.342 GPa [16].

2.2 Melt processing

Nano-phased carbon whiskers and polyethylene powder were carefully measured in the ratio of 2:98 by weight. The dry mixing of polyethylene powder with carbon whiskers were carried out in a mechanical blender at the highest available speed of the blender for an hour [[11]. At this time the mixture took a gray appearance and it seemed that the whiskers were thoroughly mixed with the polyethylene. In order to avoid temperature rise, which may result in the melting of the polyethylene, the mixing process was paused for 15 minutes after 10 minutes of continuous mixing and then resumed for further mixing. This technique was repeated 5 to 6 times until satisfactory mixing was observed.

Polyethylene and carbon whiskers mixture was then extruded using a *Wayne Yellow Label Table Top Extruder*. The extruder has a 19 mm diameter screw, which is driven by a 2 HP motor via toothed timing belt for smooth speed reversal and encased inside the barrel. Thermostatically controlled five heating zones were used to melt the mixture prior to extrusion; three of which were occupied by the barrel zone and rest of the two were by the die zone. The heaters inside the barrel zone were placed at the feed hopper side, center and die zone side of the barrel and set at a temperature of 149°C, 154°C and 160°C respectively. The purpose of these three heaters is to maintain gradually increasing temperature in the molten mass. The process begins when the nanophased dry-mixed powder are poured through the feed hopper to get inside the barrel zone of the extruder. As soon as they reach the barrel zone, polyethylene starts melting due to high barrel temperature. At this stage the whiskers are randomly distributed within the liquid matrix. The outer surface of the screw is designed to maintain close fit with the barrel inner surface. As a result, the molten mass cannot escape from the screw surface and are trapped inside the screw segment. As the extruder screw rotates, this molten matrix is slightly mixed with the whiskers, conveyed in a spiral pattern and finally reaches the screw end which is located immediately before the die zone. The screw end is shaped in such a way that it allows the flowing mass to escape through a narrow openings at high velocity. As the screw rotation is continued, the high velocity liquid experiences enormous shear force. The shear force at this high temperature can alter the chemical and thermal properties of the polyethylene and also the orientation of rod-shaped whiskers. It is assumed that the whiskers are partially aligned at this stage. The partially aligned whisker containing liquid polyethylene now enters the die zone which is constructed with a circular plate, 10 cm long steel tubing with 4 mm inner diameter and the die itself. The two heaters at this zone are set at a temperature of 160°C to maintain constant temperature of the flowing mass. One of the heaters is placed after the circular plate and the other one is placed immediately before the die. The circular plate is 15 mm in diameter and contains about 20 orifices, each of which is 2 mm in diameter. As the bulk materials are passing through the plate, they are disintegrated into several branches, and then combined again. This ensures a distributive mixing of the whiskers with polyethylene [19-20]. Now partially aligned whiskers containing liquid polyethylene are passed thru the 10 cm long steel tube and arrive close to the die. It should be noted that in order to ensure proper alignment of fiber, the size of the die plate and the diameter of the die opening are very critical. Hence, a special type of die was used in this process which is shown in the Fig. 1. It can be seen from the figure that the die has a converging inlet and narrow outlet (0.25 mm). This die configuration generates two distinct flow regimes that highly affect the fiber alignments. First, the converging die inlet introduces a converging flow pattern which in turn aligns the fibers along the stream line direction. Second, the narrow orifice allows the flow pattern to transform into shear flow as it enters the narrow orifice. The shear flow

produces additional fiber alignment due to differential shear rate along the boundary layer that orients the fibers in the direction of flow [7].

The process is continuous and the composite filaments with constant tension were extruded at a screw speed of 5 rpm and feed rate of approximately 50 g/h. Filaments were allowed to travel about 60-80 cm in still air (temperature 20°C) from the die outlet to a set of tension rollers, winder guide rollers, then wound on a spool using *Wayne Desktop Filament Winder* at a winding speed of 25 rpm. The process temperature, speed ratio between the winder and extruder screw, position of the roller guide, and filament travel distance, all these factors control the draw ratio λ (ratio of die orifice diameter to filament final diameter) of the process as well as the continuity of the filaments.

Figure 1: Side View of the extruder die

As polyethylene can be readily solidified and cooled as soon as it comes from extruder die outlet, room temperature air was quite satisfactory for filament extrusion. The process is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the extrusion process

2.3 Stacking and Consolidation

To come up with a nano composite panel, the extruded filaments were cut into desired length, numbers and layers and then stacked. The filament stack was then assembled with layers of porous teflon on the top and bottom, followed by bleeder cloths and Aluminum Caul plates. The whole setup was then placed for consolidation in a *Tetrahedron MTP Press Compression Molder* at a mold temperature of 122°C and pressure load of 20 lb_f for three hours. Then the material was allowed to cool to room temperature in two hours using the in-built water-cooling system.

The resulting hot pressed nanocomposites panel was approximately 1-1.5 mm thick. Using the same consolidation cycle and lay-up sequences, a control panel was also made from extruded neat polyethylene filaments. In another attempt, whiskers were dry-mixed with Polyethylene powder, and the mixture was consolidated directly to make panels. This particular step did not include any extrusion.

2.4 Testing Procedures

To estimate the size and shape, the carbon whiskers were examined using *JEOL JSM 5800* Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). As received carbon whiskers were placed on a carbon double-sided tape and coated with gold to prevent charge build-up by the electron absorbed by the specimen. Twenty five kilovolt accelerating voltage was applied to accomplish desired magnification.

Fiber alignment within the composite panel was observed by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) using *Phillips-201*. In this process the samples were cut precisely using ultramicrotome and placed on a conventional carbon coated copper grid.

Crystallinity of the polyethylene and the carbon whiskers as well as the fabricated composite panel (both extruded and powder consolidated) were verified from the X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns. The XRD measurements were carried out with a *Rigaku D/MAX 2200* X-Ray Diffractometer. The sample was trimmed at a 1 cm square and placed on the in-built platform. The characteristic XRD diffraction pattern was collected and matched with established data from *PDF* files.

In order to obtain the information on the stability of the polyethylene and carbon whisker-polyethylene composite samples, Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) was carried out under nitrogen gas atmosphere on a *TA Instruments, Inc.* apparatus. The samples were cut into small pieces using *ISOMET Cutter*. Then the samples were machined using the mechanical grinder to maintain the sample weight within 5 to 15 mg range. Next the samples were kept in a platinum sample pan, weighed and heated to 1000°C from room temperature at a heating rate of 10°C/min. The real time characteristic curves were generated by *Universal Analysis 2000-TA Instruments, Inc.* data acquisition system.

Tensile tests were conducted on a *Rheometric Minimat* tensile tester with 1 kN Load Cell. Test coupons were first cut from the compression-molded sheet, and then machined by mechanical grinder. The resulting specimen size was 50 mm × 10 mm × 1.25 mm with a gauge length of 30 mm. Total four types of samples were prepared for testing. The ultimate tensile strength and the modulus were measured at a crosshead speed of 1.25 mm/min. Property values reported here represent an average of at least three specimens in each category.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Morphological Studies

SEM micrographs of carbon whiskers are shown in Fig. 3(a). The figure clearly shows that the carbon whiskers have diameter ranging from 2-9 μm. At higher magnifications (Fig. 3(b)), the presence of nanoparticles can be observed. Figure 4 displays the XRD patterns of a) carbon whisker and b) carbon-whisker/polyethylene filaments consolidated at 122°C. In Fig 4(a) a wide peak at 26°, 2 theta represents that carbon whisker is semi-crystalline in nature. The other higher angle diffractions are not very prominent. The reason for this could be the presence of larger amount of amorphous carbon whisker and carbon nanoparticles. The main 100% peak of carbon matches that of PDF (card no 26.1076). Figure 4(b) shows the XRD diffraction patterns of polyethylene powder and samples of carbon-whisker/polyethylene both consolidated and extruded. The XRD diffraction patterns again match that of polyethylene (pdf file no: 11-0834). These results clearly indicate that the carbon-whisker/polyethylene composite material is partially

crystalline in nature. The wide peak at 26° , 2-theta corresponding to the carbon was overshadowed by strong polyethylene peaks. It is noticed that the higher intensities of peaks were observed for the extruded samples whereas the lower peak intensities were observed for consolidated ones. The higher intensities of peak suggest that higher degree of crystallinity was due to extrusion.

Figure 5(a) depicts the TGA curves of neat polyethylene and consolidated carbon-whisker/polyethylene composites. It is observed that both samples are stable up to 511°C and 510°C respectively, however, pure as-received polyethylene samples are only stable up to 489°C [16]. These temperature differences are obviously due to partial cross-linking during the consolidation process. In the contrary, TGA curves of extruded samples as shown in Fig. 5(b) are somewhat different. The figure shows that these samples are stable up to 539°C and 543°C respectively. The higher stability of extruded sample indicates that the higher percentage of cross-linking takes place during the extrusion process under the high temperature and pressure conditions. The higher stabilities are also observed for extruded samples as compared to that of non-extruded samples. These results confirm that the extrusion process enhanced the thermal stability of the composites. The highest stability was however, observed for the extruded samples as compared to any other samples. To further investigate the possibility of alignment, Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) studies were conducted as shown in Fig. 6. The black spots represent the embedded whiskers in the polyethylene matrix. The picture clearly shows that the carbon whiskers are aligned in a regular unidirectional manner.

Figure 3: scanning electron micrograph of a) as-prepared carbon whiskers
b) At higher magnification to show the nano sized particle

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: XRD Patterns of a) as-prepared carbon whisker and b) the as-prepared carbon whisker-polyethylene consolidated at 122°C.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: TGA curves of a) Neat Polyethylene and whisker-polyethylene composite, non-extruded, b) Neat Polyethylene and whisker-polyethylene composite, Extruded.

3.2 Tensile Response

Two categories of materials, namely neat and nanophased were tested under tension. As mentioned earlier, two types of nanophased samples, namely extruded samples and dry-mixed powder consolidated samples were tested. Stress-strain curves for neat and nanophased samples are shown in Fig. 7. Tensile data in tabular form is shown in Table 1. It is observed in Fig. 7 that the failure stress of the extruded polyethylene sample doped with carbon whiskers is about 17% higher than the neat extruded sample. In an average as shown in Table-1, the gain in tensile strength is 16.9%. On the other hand, the improvement in tensile modulus due to nanoparticles infusion is around 16%. Such gain in modulus is obviously a result of the high modulus of the nanowhiskers and can be predicted using rule of mixture for short fiber composites. However, the enhancement in strength by about 15-16% was somewhat surprising since that was not the usual case with vapor grown fibers studied earlier in the previous references. Usually, enhancement up

to this scale was obtained only when significant percentage (about 5-10%) of fillers were added [7, 8].

Figure 6: TEM micrograph of Carbon-whisker reinforced polyethylene composites.

To further investigate this matter, we carefully observed the stress-strain diagram of both neat and nanophased samples. As seen in Fig. 7, when neat polyethylene sample was loaded in tension, initially the stress increased linearly with displacement up to approximately 30% of the peak stress, and then exponentially until it reached the peak stress. At this stage about 12% elongation of the material was observed. Then the specimen continued to elongate while the stress remain almost unchanged. After elongating by another 30%, the material necked and failed somewhat in a ductile manner, which is typical with a semi-crystalline.

On the other hand, the stress strain diagram of the nanophased specimen suggests that the material failed immediately after reaching the peak stress at an elongation-to break far less than the neat specimen. This can be explained in the following way.

Table 1: Tensile properties of various samples.

Type	Tensile Strength, MPa	Gain/Loss [%] in Strength	Tensile Modulus, MPa	Gain/Loss [%] in Modulus
Nanocomposites [filament direction]	11.287	16.9	270	16.37
Powder Consolidated	9.362	-3.03	229	-1.29
Neat Polyethylene	9.655	-	232	-

When tensile load is applied to the short-fiber reinforced composite samples, the load is transferred to the fiber by a shearing mechanism between the fiber and the matrix, since the matrix has a lower modulus; the longitudinal strain in the matrix is higher than that of the adjacent fibers. If a perfect bond is assumed between the two constituents, the difference in longitudinal strain creates a shear stress distribution across the fiber/matrix interface. The high strength of a composite can be experienced if interfacial bonding can overcome this developed shear stress. If fibers within the composite remain highly oriented and the fiber aspect ratio exceeds the critical fiber length at an order of magnitude, the fiber carries 90 percent of the composite load, resulting high composite strength [17]. As we mentioned earlier, the material we used as reinforcement contains rod-shaped whiskers as well as nano-sized particles. It is believed that the combined contribution of the two different size particles lead to enhancement in strength even at lower volume fractions. The presence of aligned rod-shaped fibers ensures above stated strengthening mechanism and hence increased the strength. However, this percentage of enhancement was not realized before with the infusion of 2% of micron-sized particle as stated in the earlier references. We believe that the increased strength is achieved due to the presence of additional nano sized particles within the whisker bulk mass. We know that a polymer consists of long-chain molecules and the backbones of these chains are constructed by atoms, which are held together by strong covalent bonds. However, the high strength in polymers is not experienced

because the molecular chains exist primarily as random coils. From fracture mechanics point of view, the response of a semi-crystalline polymer to an external force is mainly through the motion of the chain segments of the coils which eventually lead to development and propagation of micro cracks [18]. Hence, strength of a material is highly dependent on these micro cracks, their geometry, propagation rate, growth rate and especially on the constraints that resists its growth and propagation.

Figure 7: Tensile Stress-Strain diagram of various samples

It is believed that the crack propagation can be delayed with the presence of nano-sized particle. The stress strain diagram from Fig. 7 reveals that polyethylene becomes stiffer with the infusion of nano particles. As a result it offered more resistance to deformation, slippage and crack propagation of the polymer coils. At the same time, the nanoparticle embedded in the polymer may deflect the initial cracks along their interfaces, hence delayed the rapid crack propagation. Moreover, at elevated temperature, the dispersed nanowhiskers within the matrix are extruded into filament with high shear stress; then wound with sufficient tension. These high shear stress during extrusion and the subsequent tension during winding cause cross-linking of the matrix materials.

Again, at high temperature nanowhiskers and the molten matrix undergo thermal expansion and upon cooling the reinforcing nanowhiskers shrink to a lesser extent than the matrix material. This thermal expansion mismatch leads to self-locking of the whiskers and the polyethylene at their interfaces that eventually leads to high interfacial bonding.

The above stated strengthening mechanism will not hold good if the dispersion of the nanowhiskers is not uniform. A non-uniform dispersion leads to local agglomeration of nanoparticle within the matrix. So, the bulk material will have two types of interfaces; namely, fiber-matrix and fiber-fiber interfaces. The interfacial strength between the fiber and matrix may be satisfactory but the interfacial strength between the fiber-fiber interfaces due to agglomeration of fibers will be very poor. Under applied load, this material would fail due to this poor fiber-fiber interfacial bonding. When the nano particle and the matrix are mixed physically and the mixture is directly consolidated to nanocomposite material, the uniform dispersion of the nano particle is not ensured. The reinforcing nanowhiskers are randomly oriented and also tend to entangle within the matrix. As a result, the strength of the powder-consolidated nanocomposite is less than the neat powder consolidated system as seen in Fig. 7.

4. SUMMARY

The following are the summary of the above investigation:

1. A methodology using hot extrusion has been introduced to manufacture nanophased polyethylene filaments.

2. SEM and TEM studies have indicated that initial dry mixing followed by extrusion under high shear force ensures uniform dispersion and alignment of nano-whiskers and particles in a unidirectional manner along the length of the filaments.
3. These nanophased filaments were later consolidated in a compression molding machine and made into nanocomposites.
4. Nanocomposites fabricated in this fashion were found to possess higher tensile strength and modulus by about 15-17% when compared with neat polyethylene control samples. While the enhancement in modulus was expected, the gain in strength was somewhat surprising and is believed have been caused by the alignment of nanoparticles and whiskers during the extrusion process.
5. Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) has also indicated that nano infusion increases the thermal stability and crystallinity of the system which eventually translate into higher mechanical properties.
6. Finally, it has been demonstrated that a relatively significant gain in structural strength and stiffness can be achieved in a thermoplastic system by infusing only 2% by weight of nanoparticles and whiskers through a simple extrusion process.

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